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Research Article

A Study on Incidence of Dengue and Efficacy of Caripill a Papaya Extract in Mild and Moderate Cases in a Tertiary Care Hospital

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ABSTRACT

Dengue is a mosquito borne viral infection with major complication thrombocytopenia. According to WHO, high incidence of dengue over 6.5 million cases with more than 7300 dengue related deaths were reported in 2023. This study aimed to assess the incidence of dengue and effect of Caripill, a papaya leaf extract in augmented clinical outcomes in moderately affected dengue patients in a tertiary care center. A prospective observational study conducted from May 2023 to april 2024 in Durgabai Deshmukh Hospital & Research Center, Vidyanagar Hyderabad. A total of seventy-five Patients enrolled were treated with Caripill and followed up daily for 5 days with monitoring platelet and other hematological parameters. Total subjects were evaluated for efficacy and safety. All the subjects significantly increased their platelet count from 80,800 on Day 1 to 116,093 on Day 5; (P = 0.0001) and improved hemoglobin levels, RBC levels, and systolic blood pressure. Symptoms were typical of dengue with fever, myalgia, and dyspnea being most prevalent. Caripill significantly increased the platelet count and selective hematologic improvements that could make it an adjunct therapy for dengue.

INTRODUCTION

Dengue fever is a viral disease transmitted by Aedes mosquito with clinical symptoms from mild fever to severe manifestations, including dengue hemorrhagic fever and dengue shock syndrome. With increasing global incidence, effective

management strategies are much needed. Caripill, a preparation prepared from papaya leaf is effective in managing dengue infection.^{1,2,3} The rationale for its use in the management of dengue infections primarily lies in its potential in increasing platelet counts, which is critical in preventing complications of severe dengue.⁴

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Immune modulation is one mechanism of action, as the compounds increase the body's immunity to infections, even viruses such as dengue⁵. Its anti-inflammatory action helps in reducing excessive inflammatory responses and thus reduces tissue damage. In addition, antioxidant activity prevents oxidative stress; hence, it protects the cells from damage during viral infections.⁶ Carica papaya is considered safe for most individuals; however, few side effects have been reported such as mild gastrointestinal upset.⁷

Therefore, the public health implications of Caripill as a supplemental treatment for dengue are excellent, especially in resource-limited settings where the only approach to conventional treatment may not be feasible.⁸ By providing insights into the incidence of dengue and the potential benefits of alternative therapies like Caripill, the research contributes to the broader understanding of dengue management in resource-limited settings.^{9,10}

METHODOLOGY:

A prospective observational study conducted in Durgabai Deshmukh Hospital & Research Centre, Hyderabad for 6 months in patients with mild to moderate dengue associated with thrombocytopenia. A total of 75 subjects diagnosed with dengue were enrolled and distributed based on demographic factors like age, gender, educational status, employment status, and area of residence. Admission records of clinical signs and symptoms like fever, myalgia, headache, and dyspnea were recorded. Patients were also assessed for body mass index, comorbidities like diabetes and hypertension, and social habits like smoking and alcohol consumption. For further diagnosis and liver involvement or other complications, serological tests like Ns1, IgM, and IgG were used along with USG imaging.

Baseline measurements of physiological parameters, which included respiratory rate, pulse, and blood pressure, along with blood values, were done in the form of haemoglobin, RBC, total leukocyte count, hematocrit, and levels of SGPT and SGOT. The follow-up measurements were done on Day 5 to see if changes were occurring after treatment. The platelet counts were measured on a daily basis from the baseline of Day 1 until Day 5 to study the effect of Caripill on the recovery of platelets.

All data have therefore been analysed for statistical significance in differences observed over time, especially concerning improvements in platelet count and other blood parameters. The overall methodology used in the study enabled an in-depth analysis of the efficacy of Caripill in dengue treatment because of systematic recording of clinical symptoms, diagnostic findings, and progression in key physiological and haematological markers.

RESULTS

Incidence of Dengue :

Incidence rate of dengue was calculated to measure the new cases occurring within a five-month time frame among the patient's population within the hospital. Within the five-month admission to the hospital, 11,000 patients were admitted, where 75 new cases of dengue occurred. Using an incidence rate calculator, the dengue incidence in this population was computed to be 6.818 cases per 1,000 people. This estimate provides insight into the likelihood of dengue occurrence in this particular hospital setting for the period of the study, making it a great metric for understanding and managing dengue transmission in similar healthcare environments.

Subject Characteristics:

Table no.1 describes about the demographics, social, and clinical features of the patients involved in this study. 34 were females (45%) and 41 were males (55%). 26.7% were aged 20 years or below, 29.3% were between 21-30 years, and the largest group, 44%, were aged 31-40 years. Among the patients, 40% were literate, and 60% were illiterate. about 61.3% of the patients were employed, and 38.7% were unemployed. Most of the patients belonged to an urban area, and only

25.3% belonged to a rural area. Fever was a common symptom (100%), myalgia (64%), dyspnea (64%), headache (58.7%), and arthralgia (53.3%), among others. 29.3% fell under the normal BMI category, 42.7% obese, and 28% overweight. Diabetes and hypertension are the comorbidities observed in 9.3% of the patients. In this study, 24% were smokers, and 14.7% admitted alcohol use.

Table No 1 : Subject Characteristics

Subject Characteristics		No. of patients	Percentage (%)
Gender	Female	34	45
	Male	41	55
Age	<=20	20	26.7
	21 - 30	22	29.3
	31 - 40	33	44
Educational status	Literate	30	40
	Illiterate	45	60
Employment status	Employed	46	61.3
	Unemployed	29	38.7
Area of residence	Rural	19	25.3
	Urban	56	74.7
Clinical signs and symptoms	Fever	75	100
	Headache	44	58.7
	Myalgia	48	64
	Arthralgia	40	53.3
	Nausea and vomiting	48	64
	Yellow discoloration of skin	29	38.7
	Dyspnea	48	64
	Sore throat	46	61.3
	Epistaxis	23	30.7
	Hematuria	21	28
	Weakness	50	66.7
	Melena	25	33.3
	Rashes	25	33.3
BMI status	Normal	27	29.3
	Obesity	44	42.7
	Overweight	29	28
Comorbidities	Diabetes	7	9.3
	Hypertension	7	9.3
Social habits	Smoking	18	24
	Alcohol	11	14.7

Diagnostic Tests and Length of Hospital stay:

Table No.2 provides about the diagnostic results along with the duration of inpatient stay. 37.3% of the patients were Ns1 positive, 38.7% IgM

positive and 24% IgG positive indicating serological variation of study population. Ascites was present in 6.7%, GB wall edema in 4%, hepatomegaly in 9.3%, splenomegaly in 8%, and 72% having normal USG results. The length of stay ranged from 1 to 6 days. Most patients were spent 4 days, with 42.7 percent being spent for 3 days in the hospital.

hospital stay	4 days	44	58.7
	5 days	75	100
	6 days	12	16

Table No 2: Diagnostic Tests and Length of Hospital stay

Diagnostic Tests and Length of Hospital stay		No. of patients	Percentage (%)
Serology	Ns1 positive	28	37.3
	IgM positive	29	38.7
	IgG positive	18	24
USG findings	Ascites	5	6.7
	Gb wall edema	3	4
	Hepatomegaly	7	9.3
	Splenomegaly	6	8
	Normal	54	72
Length of	1 day	8	10.7
	2 days	16	21.3
	3 days	93	124

Effects Of Carica Papaya (Caripill) On Different Parameters/ Blood Values in Dengue Patients:

This table no.3 assesses the effects of Caripill on some physiological and blood parameters of patients diagnosed with dengue at baseline and Day 5. There was a variation in respiratory rate, from 20.64 to 21.06, and pulse rate that shifted from 82.88 to 82.56; no significant difference resulted. A considerable decrease was determined in the systolic blood pressure, from 116 to 109.64; P = 0.003, diastolic blood pressure, however, was seen non-significantly. Hemoglobin increased significantly from 13.06 to 13.71 (P = 0.02), RBC levels increased significantly from 4.07 to 4.4 (P = 0.0001), and all the other parameters like total leukocyte count, hematocrit, SGPT, and SGOT did not show much of a change.

Table 3: Effects Of Carica Papaya (Caripill) On Different Parameters/ Blood Values in Dengue Patients

Parameters	Mean, Standard Deviation	Baseline	Day 5	P value
Respiratory rate	Mean	20.64	21.06	0.13
	Std Dev	2.16	1.05	
Pulse rate	Mean	82.88	82.56	0.81
	Std Dev	8.31	8.74	
Systolic Blood Pressure	Mean	116	109.64	0.003*
	Std Dev	12.08	13.99	
Diastolic Blood pressure	Mean	75.4	71.8	0.08
	Std Dev	8.26	8.33	
Heamoglobin	Mean	13.06	13.71	0.02*
	Std Dev	2.14	1.27	
Total Leucocyte Count	Mean	7213.3	7666.6	0.42
	Std Dev	3702.7	3235.5	
RBC Levels	Mean	4.07	4.4	0.0001*
	Std Dev	0.233	0.21	
Hematocrit Levels	Mean	34.6	35.81	0.39
	Std Dev	8.71	8.64	
SGPT Levels	Mean	59.52	47.5	0.18
	Std Dev	71.83	30	
SGOT Levels	Mean	57.17	50.93	0.29
	Std Dev	42.99	28.21	

Effect of Carica Papaya (Caripill) On Platelet Values in Dengue Patients:

Table no. 4 shows the effect of Caripill on platelet counts in patients with dengue, recorded from baseline, Day 1, until Day 5. A progressive increase in mean platelet count was seen in the patients from Day 1 to Day 5, with significant daily increases. Each day demonstrated statistically significant improvement in platelet count ($P = 0.0001$) when compared to Day 1; thus, the study opens the possibility that Caripill may be effective in augmenting platelet counts in the mild to moderate form of dengue cases.

Table 4 : Effect of Carica Papaya (Caripill) On Platelet Values in Dengue Patients

DAYS / PLATELET COUNT	MEAN	STD DEV	P value
DAY 1 (BASELINE)	80800	4535	NA
DAY 2	84600	2746	Day 1 to Day 2 Change - P value : 0.0001
DAY 3	88600	500	Day 1 to Day 3 Change - P value : 0.0001
DAY 4	89718	405	Day 1 to Day 4 Change - P value : 0.0001
DAY 5	116093	5750	Day 1 to Day 5 Change - P value : 0.0001

DISCUSSION

This study examined the prevalence of dengue and the clinical effects of Caripill, an extract from papaya leaves, in patients with dengue fever. The incidence of dengue was calculated and found to be 6.818 cases per 1,000 individuals. This fairly high incidence calls for the proper preventive measure and therapeutic intervention for the control of dengue cases in the same health care settings, especially in the peak outbreak periods. The demographic data reflects a balanced

distribution among both sexes, while 55% are males with an area of concentration mostly within the ages 21-40 years. Most of the patients, 74.7%, came from an urban background-most likely in the areas with the highest population density, where most dengue transmission has been recorded. This also results in increased exposure to sites of the vector's breeding.¹¹

Clinical presentations of the patients included manifestations typical for the common disease; all showed fever as the most universal symptom. Other common symptoms were myalgia (64%), dyspnea (64%), headache (58.7%), and arthralgia (53.3%). Thus, these symptoms reflect typical dengue symptomatology and demonstrate the wide spectrum of clinical presentation of dengue, which complicates early diagnosis and management. The distribution of BMI was suggestive of a significant proportion of overweight or obese patients that could plausibly affect the immune response and disease progression and may be associated with BMI that affects the severity of disease, although more work is to be done to establish such claims. Social habits such as smoking and alcohol consumption were reported in patients, and 24% were noted to be smokers and 14.7% alcohol consumers, but whether such impacts dengue outcomes cannot be ascertained.¹²

Diagnostic evaluation confirmed the diagnosis of dengue and clinical evaluation. Serological examination revealed 37.3% NsI positivity, 38.7% IgM positivity, and 24% IgG positivity; this varied range of the stages of immune response in the study group. The ultrasound findings like hepatomegaly and splenomegaly were present in a very few patients, which was indicative of mild to moderate organ involvement seen in most dengue cases in this population.^{13,14} This treatment produced remarkable alterations in the physiological parameters and blood values.

Improvement in the count of platelets within the five-day course of treatment was remarkable; the mean counts improved from 80,800 on Day 1 to 116,093 on Day 5 ($P = 0.0001$); such change makes Caripill a potential agent in supporting platelet recovery, a pivotal concept in dengue management. Other vital changes were noted in systolic blood pressure, from 116 to 109.64; $P = 0.003$, hemoglobin from 13.06 to 13.71; $P = 0.02$, and RBC count from 4.07 to 4.4; $P = 0.0001$, all of which indicate that Caripill has a positive impact on the hematological values of dengue patients. Other parameters, pulse rate, and levels of SGPT/SGOT showed nonsignificant changes, meaning that Caripill's effect is more specific toward the support of platelet as well as RBC rather than affecting general systemic markers.^{15,16,17}

This study has shown the incidence and clinical profile of dengue in a tertiary care setting while demonstrating the promising role of Caripill in enhancing platelet recovery and improving select hematological parameters in dengue patients. These results indicate that an adjunctive role of Caripill may be of use in the treatment of dengue fever, which will be evaluated further in large trials through long-term patient outcomes. The high incidence rate of this disease emphasizes the necessity of continuing public health efforts in controlling dengue transmission, especially in urban areas where the vulnerability may be higher.¹⁸

CONCLUSION

The study established an incidence rate of 6.818 dengue cases per 1,000 persons in a tertiary care hospital for a period of five months, thereby reiterating the threat posed by dengue infection that persists. Clinical presentation is supportive of the classical presentation of dengue and diverse demographic profiles, and Caripill treatment has

been very effective, especially regarding platelet counts. Five-day evidence of significant improvement of both platelet counts and vital hematological parameters underscores an important role of Caripill in the treatment and management of mild to moderate dengue cases. Such outcomes of the study indicate the application of Caripill could be useful as adjunct treatment in dengue although large-scale studies should be undertaken so that its efficacy may prove and treatment modalities in dengue should further be expanded.

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